

PROSPECTS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE SYSTEM OF COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOLS AND PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Samandarova Adolat

Student Uzbekistan-Finland pedagogy Institute "Preschool Education"

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Abstract. *Inclusive education is a process that aims to integrate disabled children into the educational process and adapt general education schools to disabled children, with social justice and equality as the main goal. Inclusive education includes children with special needs and disabilities not only in special schools. but admits that healthy children can be educated in general schools. For this, both the school and the teachers-educators should be ready for the inclusive education system, the level of the school, the physical conditions and the factors that make it possible to study should fully meet the requirements of this education.*

Keywords: *inclusive education, comprehensive schools, preschool education, society, forms of education, special education.*

Have you ever thought that some children can't walk the roads we walk every day, can't hear or see the beauty we see every day, the events in the world around them, because their movement is limited due to paralysis, his eyes are weak, his ears are deaf. But this child could grow up to be completely healthy and enjoy all the beauties, but he was deprived of it due to the influence of negative factors. Children who are mentally or physically disabled due to various reasons cannot be left out of society. Such children have limited opportunities due to their disabilities. He needs correctional assistance due to his limited capabilities.

Conducting correctional educational, educational and developmental work with disabled children, adapting them to the social society, bringing them to adulthood so that they can serve themselves and benefit the society to a certain extent is one of the most urgent issues of every country. is considered After all, according to the words of our president Sh.M. Mirziyoev, "The spirituality of any nation is determined by its attention to disabled people living in this society." That is why the full implementation of these tasks needs special support. In order to support children's rights and introduce them, "Inclusive education" has risen to the level of international law, including the 1989 UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Dakar Declaration, It is reflected in the Salamanca Declaration and the Work Plan (1994). However, many children with special needs are left out of education. The main reasons for this are, first of all, the lack of attention of parents to their children, and then, the lack of educational institutions for teaching this child in the area or they are located too far away. This is a very sad situation for a child with special needs. Because this child's opportunities are limited due to the existing defect, it is known that if the child does not receive education and the correction of the defect is not carried out, the level of the defect will become more severe, secondary defects will appear and his self-service will become more difficult. skills are not formed. It becomes difficult to adapt to social life. In short, he remains "disabled". In turn, the increase in the number of disabled people in the society slows down the development of this society. In order to avoid such consequences and fully ensure the rights of

children in need of special assistance, the issues of introducing inclusive education are becoming widespread.

Special education has developed as an educational system for children with disabilities. It is built on the assumption that the needs of children with disabilities cannot be met in general education institutions and preschools. Special education operates all over the world in the form of schools or boarding schools, as well as small parts of general schools. Education of children with special needs in the special education system makes it difficult for them to adapt to society after finishing school. It also forces them to stay away from their families. This category of children gets used to being neglected, they have difficulties in self-care. In addition, many children with special needs are excluded from education. Currently, in our Republic, inclusive education policy is being implemented in order to make children with special needs receive education in special or general education system according to their development level, characteristics of disabilities and abilities. Placing a disabled child in a normal environment is the first step towards integration. Inclusive education is based on the social model, which believes that the problem is not in the child, but in the program and methodology. This requires making some changes to the education system. In this case, educational plans are prepared taking into account the needs of each child, and aspects of the methodology related to psychological problems are put on the right track. Inclusive education assumes that all children, including children with disabilities, can attend the school of their choice. The child wraps himself in his blanket. He forgets to communicate with the environment. Society, environment, misunderstandings and mistakes caused the child to become disabled. Therefore, this society must sacrifice itself for his education. In inclusive education, physical conditions in school and pre-school education also play an important role. To put it simply, students enter the doors of all schools and preschools through stairs. But disabled children in special wheelchairs cannot climb these stairs, even children walking on crutches may have difficulty. Therefore, it is necessary to create comfortable conditions for healthy children and disabled children to pass through the stairs and doors.

Inclusive education allows children with special needs to always be in their family neighborhood and in the circle of relatives. Placement of children in boarding schools far away from their family and home prevents their right to participate in the life of their home, family and community. A child who is far from his home, family, and parental love grows up with a hard time. Because the family is the main center of education. Inclusive education can serve as a catalyst for improving the quality of education. Admission of children with special needs to general education and pre-school educational institutions encourages students to develop new teaching methods that are more child-centered and involve more students. And the benefit of this affects every child. Inclusive education helps prevent discrimination. Misconceptions and attitudes towards people with disabilities are very high in society. The lack of information about them and their closed education in special institutions from a young age may be the reason for this. Losing or reducing such an attitude is a very difficult task. But it is known from experience that compared to adults, children understand differences and similarities faster. If children with special needs were educated together with children with normal development, it would ensure that all children with disabilities would realize that they are children like themselves and would not be discriminated against. One of the most urgent problems today is the issue of important tasks and the situation in the system related to children in need of social protection. After Uzbekistan gained independence, deep reforms and changes are taking place in the system of social protection of

children, as in all areas. The interpretation of new ideas on inclusive education requires national, organizational and methodological reforms. Currently, inclusive education is developing not only in school and pre-school education, but also in higher educational institutions. And everyone is getting the same education in the same environment.

However, the introduction of inclusive education in preschool education is difficult and may cause some protests. Because the parents of some healthy children do not want to be brought up in the same environment as children with limited opportunities or disabilities. For some children, learning with children with disabilities can have an impact on their psyche. In such a situation, the psychologist of the institution should have a conversation with the children and their parents.

I believe that living with children with disabilities in society should not be a problem for us, but we should treat them as mature individuals. I know a preschool. A child with congenital disabilities was placed in an institution on the recommendation of a doctor. After 1 year, the child was talking and walking like healthy children. I thought that this motivated the child to be healthy and not isolated from society. That is the goal of inclusive education. Children should feel free.

CONCLUSION: Future disruptions in the development of inclusive education will be prevented. Highly qualified teachers are critical to well-established support systems and adequate funding mechanisms.

The main goal of inclusive education is to create conditions for effective learning for students with disabilities. In this context, it is necessary to integrate and rehabilitate students with disabilities, to choose an effective type of inclusive education, taking into account the level of development of each child.

In today's rapidly developing society, education is available to all. There are children whose talent, ability, and mental potential deserve attention despite their physical limitations. Therefore, it is the honorable duty of us pedagogues not to be indifferent to their future, to raise them as worthy children of our society and country.

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